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NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS

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Abstract: The article examines the objective necessity of ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities, the main factors that contribute to their competitiveness, as well as presents the research results on innovative approaches to enhancing competitiveness in hotel operations.

Key words: tourism, service sector, competition, competitiveness, accommodation facilities, hotels, customers, innovation, marketing activity, demand.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada joylashtirish vositalarining raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashning obyektiv zarurati, joylashtirish vositalarining raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlovchi asosiy omillar hamda mehmonxonalar faoliyatida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari bo'yicha tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, xizmat ko'rsatish, raqobat, raqobatbardoshlik, joylashtirish vositalari, mehmonxonalar, mijozlar, innovatsiya, marketing faoliyati, ehtiyoj.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается объективная необходимость обеспечения конкурентоспособности средств размещения, основные факторы, обеспечивающие конкурентоспособность средств размещения, а также представлены результаты исследований по инновационным подходам к повышению конкурентоспособности в деятельности гостиничных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: туризм, сфера услуг, конкуренция, конкурентоспособность, средства размещения, гостиницы, клиенты, инновации, маркетинговая деятельность, потребность.

INTRODUCTION

The category of competitiveness has been extensively analyzed in economic literature and is defined as the ability of an enterprise or service provider to maintain its position in market conditions, develop, and attract new customers. Competitiveness for accommodation facilities is determined not only by the quality of service and pricing policy, but also by the level of adaptation to customer needs, marketing activities, and innovation.

The competitive environment in the tourism sector is multifaceted, influenced by economic, technological, cultural, and social factors. For example, in the hotel business, such elements as diversification of services, brand reputation, compliance with environmental standards, and digital transformation are important for achieving a competitive advantage.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities is considered as an important direction in scientific research in the field of tourism and the hotel business. Modern research approaches this issue from the point of view of economic efficiency, service quality, innovation management, and marketing.

In his work «The Competitive Advantage of Nations,» M. Porter characterizes competitiveness as the main driver of the economic system and defines the role of innovation and differentiation strategies in creating the advantages of enterprises. In his opinion, a competitive advantage is ensured not only through price, but also through value creation, an individual approach to customer needs, and unique services.

F. Kotler, J. Bowen and J. In their works on hotel and tourism marketing, Makens assesses the competitiveness of accommodation services in close connection with the level of customer satisfaction and the formation of brand trust. According to them, to maintain a competitive advantage in hotel marketing, it is necessary to constantly improve the quality of service and strengthen digital connections.

Smith also emphasizes the importance of innovative solutions in the hotel industry in his research "Hospitality Management and Innovation." In his opinion, the main factor in increasing competitiveness is the automation of the service process, personalization of the client experience, and integration of the principles of sustainable development.

Scientific research in European countries shows the influence of digital transformation and online platform-based booking systems on hotel competitiveness. According to them, digital technologies, along with increasing service efficiency, strengthen customer trust and stabilize market positions.

Analyzed scientific sources show that ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities is a multifactorial system, determined by the level of service quality, innovation, brand management, and adaptation to the digital economy. While international research focuses on digital technologies, innovative management, and customer-oriented service models, national scientific works place greater emphasis on human resource potential and state support mechanisms.

Thus, the analysis of the available literature requires a comprehensive approach to increasing the competitiveness of accommodation facilities, that is, a combination of economic, technological, and social factors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the issues of ensuring and increasing the competitiveness of accommodation facilities were studied on the basis of a comprehensive approach from the point of view of economic, organizational, and innovative factors of the development of the modern tourism industry. In the course of the study, a systematic analysis of the accommodation services market, its structural composition, territorial features, and trends in sustainable development was conducted. The methods of economic and social analysis, system analysis, comparative analysis, and statistical generalization were used as a methodological basis. Empirical analysis was also carried out based on existing scientific literature, state statistical data, opinions of specialists in the field, and reports of international organizations (UNWTO, WTTC).

Analysis and results

Today, accommodation facilities operating in the tourism sector face increasing competition in the market, frequent changes in customer demand, and the need to improve the quality of services. In such conditions, the stable operation and preservation of any accommodation facility's position are directly related to its level of competitiveness. Competitiveness is formed not only through the price of services, but also through the quality of services provided, the qualifications of employees, the management system, the culture of working with clients, and the ability to adapt to market requirements. Therefore, it is important to identify the factors ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities and analyze their impact on the results of activities. The following section details these factors and reveals their role and importance in hotel operations.

The main factors ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities can be grouped as follows (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Main factors ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities

Figure 1 systematically reflects the main factors ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities. These factors demonstrate the inextricable link between service quality, innovation, marketing, economic efficiency, and cultural values in the hotel business. As can be seen from the figure, ensuring competitiveness relies not on one factor, but on a complex of multifaceted, interacting elements.

The first factor, the quality of service and the qualifications of personnel, is the main criterion for the effectiveness of hotel activities. The level of customer satisfaction, the prestige of the hotel brand, and its market position are closely related to the qualifications of service personnel.

The use of innovative technologies is considered a modern driver of competitiveness and increases service efficiency through such tools as digital booking systems, automated management platforms, and personalization of the customer experience. At the same time, marketing and brand management are crucial for strengthening the corporate image in hotel operations, ensuring continuous communication with clients, and maintaining a competitive position in the market.

Price policy and economic efficiency ensure the stability of hotel services in the market. A favorable price-quality ratio for the client determines a competitive advantage, which serves to increase economic efficiency. At the same time, national traditions and cultural color ensure the uniqueness of services and create a positive emotional impression on tourists through local values.

Thus, the factors shown in Figure 1 together form a comprehensive model of the competitiveness of accommodation facilities. The scientific and practical significance of this model lies in the fact that it serves as a theoretical and practical basis for the effective organization of strategic management in the hotel business, the differentiation of services, and the achievement of dominance in the international market.

This analysis shows that the factors ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities are inextricably linked, each of which plays an important role in the sustainable development of hotel activities. While service quality and personnel qualifications determine customer satisfaction, innovation and marketing strategies ensure the adaptation of services to modern requirements. At the same time, economic efficiency and national color enhance the internal stability and external attractiveness of the hotel business.

In the context of the increasingly dynamic nature of the competitive environment in the modern tourism industry, new - innovative approaches are becoming necessary for the effective management of these factors. From this point of view, the use of innovative solutions as one of the most important directions for increasing the competitiveness of accommodation facilities is of current importance.

Innovations are the main source of increasing the efficiency of hotel operations. Innovative approaches in modern hotels are manifested in the following directions (Fig. 2):

Figure 2. Innovative approaches to increasing the competitiveness of hotels

Figure 2 systematically reflects the main innovative approaches that serve to increase competitiveness in hotel activities. These include "Smart room" systems, an eco-hotel concept based on environmental sustainability, digital marketing and artificial intelligence, and Big Data analysis. These areas are crucial for the development of the hotel business based on modern technologies and the automation of the service process.

“Smart room” systems are intelligent management solutions that ensure energy efficiency, security, and comfort in hotels. Through these systems, guests will be able to control room temperature, lighting, or service calls using a smartphone or sensor. This, along with improving the client experience, reduces hotel production costs and increases competitive advantage.

The concept of an eco-hotel, based on the principles of sustainable development, implies a model of activity that does not harm the environment. This approach not only creates a positive image in the minds of tourists, but also increases the prestige of the hotel in the international market through a “green brand.”

Digital marketing allows establishing interactive relationships with clients in hotel activities, effectively promoting services through online booking systems and social networks. At the same time, through Big Data and AI analysis, customer preferences, consumption habits, and market trends are analyzed, and personalized service strategies are developed.

Thus, the innovative approaches reflected in Figure 2 create a modern technological basis for increasing the competitiveness of the hotel business. Along with improving the quality of service and customer satisfaction, they have important scientific and practical significance in adapting hotel management to the requirements of the digital economy.

The results of the conducted research show that ensuring the competitiveness of accommodation facilities is crucial for the sustainable development of the tourism industry. Quality of service, personnel qualifications, innovative technologies in increasing competitiveness

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Ensuring competitiveness in accommodation facilities is a key factor in increasing the efficiency of the hotel business, establishing a stable position in the national tourism market, and gaining international recognition. To maintain a competitive advantage in the modern hotel industry, it is necessary to constantly improve the quality of service, effectively use innovation and digital technologies, and ensure an individual approach to customer needs.

According to the results of the analysis, the introduction of innovative approaches in the hotel business - the use of digital marketing, «smart room» systems, environmentally friendly hotel models, and methods of analysis based on artificial intelligence - makes it possible to increase service efficiency. This will serve to ensure customer satisfaction, strengthen competitive advantages in the market, and enhance the international prestige of the national tourism sector.

At the same time, the widespread introduction of innovations in the activities of accommodation facilities, the regular improvement of personnel qualifications, the introduction of digital management systems, and the development of hotel models based on environmental principles will remain an important priority at the next stage of the industry's development.

The research results confirm that ensuring competitiveness requires not only an economic approach, but also the formation of a comprehensive management system covering social, innovative, and environmental aspects.

Based on the results of scientific research, when increasing the competitiveness of hotels and similar accommodation facilities, it is advisable to pay attention to the following:

- implementation of special educational programs to improve the qualifications and service culture of personnel in the hotel industry;
- expansion of digital transformation and automation in the activities of accommodation facilities;
- strengthening the tourist image of the country through the development of hotels with national brands;
- modernization of tourism infrastructure based on public-private partnership;
- regular monitoring of customer feedback and alignment of service quality with ISO standards.

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